

The Influence of Innovative Entrepreneurship Education on the Student's Entrepreneurial Behavior: Literature Review

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Abstract: Entrepreneurship education in colleges and universities has attracted worldwide attention as an innovative method for nurturing potential. China has adopted innovative entrepreneurship as a national policy to stimulate economic growth. In order to effectively implement the innovation-driven development strategy and enhance the quality, efficiency, and progress of the economy, it is necessary to further advance the reform of entrepreneurial education in colleges and universities, with a focus on fostering innovation. The General Office of the State Council of China has also issued guidance on supporting innovative entrepreneurship among college students. This viewpoint advocates for the promotion of entrepreneurship that is driven by innovation and leads to more employment opportunities. Scholars from both local and international backgrounds have extensively investigated the concept of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. This study expands on the current body of research by incorporating and extracting shared aspects of entrepreneurial self-efficacy, specifically the ability to see opportunities, innovate, and coordinate relationships. However, researchers have not yet determined a clear and unified standard for classifying entrepreneurial self-efficacy into separate components. It is crucial to establish a standardized measurement system for further division. This study aims to assess the self-efficacy of students in schools in order to determine the specific aspects of entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

Introduction

College and university entrepreneurship education has garnered global interest as a creative way to develop potential. Innovative entrepreneurship has become a national policy in China as a growth driver. To implement the innovation-driven development strategy, improve the quality, efficiency, and advancement of the economy, and facilitate comprehensive higher education reform, the country must deepen the reform of innovative entrepreneurship education in colleges and universities. This change also promotes graduate entrepreneurship and employment. Since the 1980s, China's universities have focused on teaching all students entrepreneurship. Four times since 2012 (August 2012, May 2015, June 2016, and September 2021), a national-level document has promoted innovation to boost entrepreneurship and employment. Its goals are to help university students develop innovative entrepreneurial skills, increase entrepreneurship and employment opportunities for graduates, and spread innovative entrepreneurship education (Huang & Yang, 2022). In the context of "mass entrepreneurship and innovation," college students' entrepreneurial efforts support new industries, regional economic development, and economic transformation and upgrading.

Vocational and general education are distinct yet equally important. Higher vocational

colleges and universities, which make up 53% of all higher education institutions, were founded to meet local economic growth's demand for trained workers and advance regional economic and social advancement. To address regional industry needs, higher vocational education in China must integrate industry and education and develop university-industry partnership patterns.

Higher vocational colleges and universities must adopt innovative entrepreneurial education that supports regional economic development, industrial development, and industry-education integration. In the current era, this is crucial for higher vocational institutions and universities' connotative development. By providing cutting-edge entrepreneurship education, specialized courses, competitions, resources, and support, higher vocational colleges and universities encourage student-led businesses and innovation. This boosts students' employability, competitiveness, economic growth, and social innovation.

Guidance on Supporting College Students' Innovative Entrepreneurship was also released by the General Office of the State Council of China. This opinion promotes innovation-driven entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship-led employment. They help students develop innovative entrepreneurship skills, help college graduates find jobs, improve human resources, foster college students' holistic development, and increase their employment opportunities. In 2022, the General Office of the State Council of China published a guideline to help college graduates and young people find jobs and start businesses. The circular promotes deepening school reform of creative entrepreneurship education and focused training. Innovative entrepreneurship education at higher technical colleges and assistance for practical entrepreneurial activities are stressed in the policy.

Chinese government policy promotes creative entrepreneurship education. Thus, all higher vocational colleges and universities prioritize innovative entrepreneurship education. Building platforms, reinforcing the base, and guiding have been their methods. They have also strengthened the system and service environment for creative entrepreneurship education and built a campus culture that promotes innovation and entrepreneurship. These institutions have also tried to create a multi-level, systematic creative entrepreneurship education system. The university innovative entrepreneurship education evaluation research and consultancy agency developed TP3R to evaluate Chinese universities' innovative entrepreneurship education. This model evaluates each university on five essential indicators: creative entrepreneurship instruction, practice, research, effectiveness, and reputation. All schools have an advanced entrepreneurial education system, novel entrepreneurship courses, student involvement in entrepreneurship competitions, and policy support for innovative entrepreneurship.

Studying the literature and third-party entrepreneurship education rankings shows that creative entrepreneurship education at higher vocational institutions and universities is uneven. The third-party "Chuang Index" released the "2022 China University Innovative Entrepreneurship Education Index List". This consulting firm assessed the top 50 higher vocational colleges and universities' innovative entrepreneurial education. The investigation found these institutions in 20 mainland Chinese provinces, municipalities, and autonomous regions. However, certain provinces, municipalities, and autonomous regions had no top-50 colleges or universities. In addition, the top 50 higher vocational institutions and universities varied greatly among the 20 provinces, municipalities, and autonomous regions. Provinces, municipalities, and autonomous regions with top 50 vocational colleges and universities vary. Zhejiang, Guangdong, Hunan, Jiangsu, Sichuan, Anhui, Hebei, and other economically and industrially developed regions are most often chosen. Innovative entrepreneurship education is better in these places due to increased vocational education. One Guangxi school, in Liuzhou City, made the top 50. This school has strong industrial ties and advantages in University-Industry Collaboration Patterns. The literature research summarizes the problems

related to innovative entrepreneurship in higher vocational education as follows: the education system for fostering innovation abilities in higher vocational colleges is outdated, the teacher system is inadequate, there is a lack of coordination between colleges and universities, and enterprises and colleges collaborate poorly. A perfect method for fostering students' inventive and entrepreneurial skills with enterprises has not yet been developed.

McMullen & Shepherd argue that entrepreneurial behaviours are not single behaviours but a series of behaviours that are helping entrepreneurs to achieve their entrepreneurial goals, and their implementation relies heavily on the entrepreneur's own entrepreneurial intentions and perceived entrepreneurial opportunities (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006). Deng defines entrepreneurial behaviour as a set of behaviours performed by entrepreneurs to achieve their entrepreneurial goals, it is not just about being the owner of a start-up business, but any person who has been involved in activities related to the creation of a business can be regarded as carrying out entrepreneurial behaviour (Deng, 2019). It has also been argued that entrepreneurial behaviour consists of a series of interrelated processes, which are explained through the three stages of defining the dream, the business idea and the creation of the new business (Metallo, Agrifoglio, Briganti, Mercurio, & Ferrara, 2021). Activities related to participation in the creation of a business are therefore regarded as engaging in entrepreneurial behaviour. C. Li et al found that entrepreneurial passion has a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial alertness, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial behaviour. Proactive personality positively and significantly modulates entrepreneurial intention and conduct (C. Li et al., 2020). According to Yi (2021), entrepreneurial intention affects entrepreneurial conduct. Neneh (2019a) found that entrepreneurial ambition best predicts entrepreneurial action. Previous research has also found that entrepreneurial self-efficacy affects both entrepreneurial intention and behavior (Darmanto & Yuliari, 2018; Neneh, 2019b). Several studies have revealed that contextual circumstances and entrepreneurial competence strongly influence entrepreneurial activity. Other study can use entrepreneurial behavior as a dependent and independent variable. This study explores entrepreneurial behavior as an important outcome variable, concentrating on upper vocational college and university students' unique traits. Higher vocational students' business startup activities are considered entrepreneurial conduct by the study. Using entrepreneurial conduct as a dependent variable is reliable. Its independent, intermediate, and moderating variables are examined in this study.

An entrepreneurial attitude.

Due to societal and work market changes, self-employment is gaining popularity across all sectors. This has promoted "mass entrepreneurship and innovation" across society. The Chinese government values innovation and entrepreneurship. This is shown in the "Government Work Report" and the implementation of numerous programs and policies at all levels. These measures have fostered self-employment. The number of ordinary college graduates in China is predicted to reach 10.76 million in 2022, up 1.67 million from the previous year. Due to economic weakness, job supply and demand are out of balance. Thus, college graduates face difficult employment. College graduates' employment and entrepreneurship can reinvigorate society. Understanding how college and university education affects college students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy, willingness to entrepreneurship, and actual entrepreneurial behaviors is crucial to reforming innovation and entrepreneurship education.

An independent research and consulting firm evaluates Chinese colleges and universities' innovation and entrepreneurship education annually using the Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education Index (IEI). The yearly "Ranking of China's Colleges and Universities on Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education Index" is based on objective data. The rating includes the Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education Index for Chinese

undergraduate institutions and higher vocational colleges and universities. This report summarizes Chinese university innovation and entrepreneurship progress for the public. It uses third-party evaluation to help Chinese institutions develop innovation and entrepreneurship teaching. The China's Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education Index for Higher Vocational (Specialised) Colleges and Universities includes 1,489 institutions. According to 2022 data, the top 200 institutions have scores between 100 and 28.13, while the remainder 1,000 have ratings below 28. This shows that higher vocational colleges and universities provide very different innovation and entrepreneurship programs. According to 2017 and 2018 annual reports on the employment quality of graduates from four Wuhan colleges and universities, independent entrepreneurship ranged from 0.3% to 4.4%. Graduates have a low rate of independent entrepreneurship and survival. College and university innovation and entrepreneurship education reform has had varied effects (Feiyan, 2020). Chinese higher vocational colleges and universities are important in higher education due to their vast student populations. These students drive innovation and entrepreneurship, thus they must be educated in them. The predicted and actual number of entrepreneurs and their success rate are still far apart.

Entrepreneurship education is vital to a person's entrepreneurial aim. Whether someone engages in entrepreneurship depends on their entrepreneurial intention (Boahemaah, Xin, Dogbe, & Pomegbe, 2020). Many scholars agree that entrepreneurship can be taught and can influence future entrepreneurial endeavors, but there is little research on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behavior (Jinzi Zhang, Bing Li, Yanning Zhang, Chi Gong, & Ziyang Liu, 2022). The particular characteristics of students in higher vocational colleges and universities require specific ways to handle innovation and entrepreneurship education concerns. We analyze how higher vocational colleges and universities apply innovation and entrepreneurship education to determine its impact on entrepreneurial behavior. We also examine the relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial willingness, and entrepreneurial conduct to inform higher vocational college and university innovation and entrepreneurship education reform.

Literature review

Increasing emphasis on creative and entrepreneurial thinking is changing higher education. Universities are expected to teach students entrepreneurial skills to succeed in today's uncertain and competitive global economy, where technology advances rapidly. Chinese colleges should offer innovative entrepreneurship courses, according to the Ministry of Education. This has drawn attention to universities and colleges as a key to training students for the modern workforce and fostering creativity.

Merging these two fields of study has created a new field of research on how innovative university entrepreneurship programs effect students and alumni's entrepreneurial behavior. This paper examines how new entrepreneurship instruction affects students' entrepreneurial behavior in vocational higher education. It classifies existing studies on creative entrepreneurship education in tertiary vocational institutions and college and university student entrepreneurship to explore this ever-changing field. After reviewing key empirical investigations, theoretical frameworks, and conceptual contributions, future research trends, gaps, and possibilities are indicated. Also, methodologies are critiqued. Novel entrepreneurship teaching methods at postsecondary vocational institutions may help us understand the many factors that influence entrepreneurship.

Higher vocational education is a mix of the two. The expansion of university vocational and technical education programs is linked to the nationwide demand for highly skilled technical personnel. Four stages have shaped China's higher vocational education system. Integrating adult higher education, vocational education, and specialized education began in 1998–2000.

This sort of schooling was called "higher vocational" and "higher specialized education" throughout this time (Sen, 2013). The era of standardized management (2001–2005) introduced a single professional catalogue and management approaches to oversee professional surroundings and talent supply. First-round operational assessments were also implemented to control school administration. This standardised management practices at vocational universities (Xiaoqing, 2022). The 2006–2013 connotation construction period saw "higher vocational education" replace "higher vocational and post-secondary education". As a result, vocational education universities and colleges have prioritized connotation creation and professional growth, according to Xiaoqing (2022). A trend toward specialized programs and improved academic standards at four-year and university institutions has increased higher education opportunities and resources (Yu, 2022). After the 2014 comprehensive reform stage, higher vocational education focused on job development beyond teaching. Thus, crucial reforms have gained priority (Yu, 2022). Undergraduates are developing Chinese-themed higher vocational institutes to improve vocational education. Merging academic and occupational courses is a cornerstone of vocational education reform. Comprehensive reform is also being proposed as a new step in vocational education.

Vocational education, including higher vocational education, aims to produce highly skilled technological experts (Yu, 2022). Beginning in 2021, higher vocational education should boost undergraduate programs while maintaining their identities. We should create a framework that blends intermediate, senior specialized, senior undergraduate, professional postgraduate, and talent cultivation requirements in undergraduate vocational programs. If we want vocational education to be more effective by 2023, we must overhaul the system and start over. This redesign aims to incorporate regional features, increase standardized development, and improve legislation and procedures that support vocational education's nurturing mode, development system, operation mechanism, and social security. It should appropriately represent technical-skills education. Furthermore, towns must consolidate their primary responsibility and establish transparent, systematic regulations on talent development programs, pedagogical techniques, practical instruction systems, and faculty. These efforts will ensure high-quality vocational education that can meet scientific, technological, and industrial advances (Mengqing & Jing, 2023). The key topics are market innovation, unmet technical needs, unsolved problems, and the "last kilometre". To make vocational education a vital role in city growth, industry and education must be better connected. The Department (2023) claims that strengthening education, talent, value, innovation, and industrial chains together will revitalize social and economic development. Explore new international collaboration methods and make higher vocational education more accessible. Higher vocational education should gradually become more transparent to better connect and facilitate social and economic progress, improve development alignment, and build a proficient society and prosperous nation with a skilled workforce, according to Xiaoqing (2022).

Most of China's universities and vocational colleges were built by provincial or municipal governments or business magnates because they promote area economy (Lu & Chen, 2022). If we want our kids to learn innovative entrepreneurship, be adaptive, creative, and dedicated, universities and vocational institutions must change talent development. Higher vocational college and university graduates will satisfy social expectations (X. G. Li, 2020). Since the 1990s, Chinese universities and vocational institutes have used creative entrepreneurship education to assist graduates find jobs in a competitive job market. Many fresh graduates are under pressure to find work, but this realistic approach will assist. Creative entrepreneurship education is popular at most Chinese higher vocational institutions and universities, according to Liming and Fengjun (2020). Most universities and HSIs prioritize creative entrepreneurship education. Due to several challenges, this region has not achieved its goal.

A lack of a solid system to educate creative minds, graduates with outdated information and no new ideas, and schools that don't foster innovation and risk-taking are all significant factors (Ding, 2021).

Over the past 30 years, innovative entrepreneurship education at universities and vocational institutions has yielded significant theoretical and practical findings. Higher vocational creative entrepreneurship programs are demanding more from students today. Xinghai (2021) anticipates ten higher vocational innovative entrepreneurial education development patterns. Raising the profile of education, especially university vocational education quality improvement, is becoming more vital. The "Programme for the Construction of High-level Higher Vocational Schools and Programmes with Chinese Characteristics" outlines the future of vocational education, and higher vocational creative entrepreneurial education will be crucial. Creative, technically capable people will benefit from this education. New entrepreneurship programmes will foster creative, technical talent (Liming & Fengjun, 2020). Vocational colleges should emphasize creative and entrepreneurial thinking. High-quality, lifelong education should be available to everybody. A comprehensive talent development program should include innovative entrepreneurship instruction for all students. Society should gain from it, not just kids. Thus, all students and the public should have access to creative entrepreneurship education (J. L. Wang, 2022). To promote employment and entrepreneurship, creative entrepreneurship education must be integrated into talent training and offered to all pupils. This education should be available to all, not just students. Social enterprise workers should receive vocational training. Meeting professional continuing education needs is also vital. Modern needs justify teaching innovative entrepreneurship in vocational higher education. Educators and students will believe "Everyone can innovate and succeed" and "mass entrepreneurship and innovation" will become mainstream. Finally, instructors and students will agree that "education of the whole area and education of the whole process" is crucial. Education and whole process education" will become the core concept of innovative entrepreneurship education. The institutional mechanism will be more perfect, and higher vocational colleges will take the main responsibility to enhance the strategic position of innovative entrepreneurship education in the development of the school, implement the "hand project", and form the organisational and management system of innovative entrepreneurship education with diversified participation, unified leadership, concerted management, openness and cooperation, synergy and high efficiency, and the experts from inside and outside of the school will participate in the high-level decision-making, management and guidance of education and teaching reform, and form a system of "whole area education and whole process education". Management and guidance of education and teaching reforms, and formation of an operation mechanism of innovative entrepreneurship education in which all organisations cooperate with each other, make joint efforts to promote, and have a sound system and internal and external synergy(Xinghai, 2021). The national policy support system will be more powerful, and the education system of innovative entrepreneurship such as curriculum, project, culture, evaluation and platform will be perfected day by day. The education mode will be more innovative, and the "three-in-one" collaborative education mode combining school, enterprise and government will become the leading mode of innovative entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges and universities(weng, 2022). The reform of teachers, teaching materials and teaching method of innovative entrepreneurship education will become an important hand to promote the high-quality development of innovative entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges and universities. The curriculum system of innovative entrepreneurship education will be constantly improved and more complete(Xia, 2020). The platform service of innovative entrepreneurship education will be more open. Evaluation of innovative entrepreneurship education is an important link to promote the self-improvement of higher vocational innovative entrepreneurship education and to achieve the improvement of innovative

entrepreneurship education performance, and to build the assessment and evaluation system at the macro, meso and micro levels, so as to make the evaluation of innovative entrepreneurship education more effective.

Deepening the reform of innovative entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges and universities is an urgent need for the implementation of the innovation-driven development strategy of the country and the promotion of economic quality, efficiency and upgrading, and it is also an important measure to promote the comprehensive reform of higher vocational education and higher-quality entrepreneurship and employment of graduates (R. Yang, 2023). Under the background of "mass entrepreneurship and innovation", the innovative entrepreneurship activities of college students are beneficial to the cultivation of new industries, the development of regional economy and economic transformation and upgrading (N. A. Thompson, Verduijn, & Gartner, 2020). However, the overall entrepreneurship rate of Chinese college students is low, and the survival rate of entrepreneurship is not high, and there are still many factors restricting the development potential of this group of entrepreneurs (X. G. Li, 2020). Innovative entrepreneurship education has become an important tool to promote the comprehensive reform of higher vocational education, which is of great practical significance to enhance the entrepreneurial behaviour of college students and promote economic progress and social employment (C. Zhao, 2020). The research on entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges is in a relatively backward situation, and not many studies have been conducted in this area (Deng, 2019). As entrepreneurship education has gradually become the teaching hotspot of innovative entrepreneurship education for students in higher vocational colleges and universities, research on the mechanism of entrepreneurship education influencing entrepreneurial behaviours of students in higher vocational colleges and universities can help to provide theoretical basis and empirical evidence for students in higher vocational colleges and universities to carry out entrepreneurship education, so as to guide the innovative entrepreneurship practice of students in higher vocational colleges and universities in a more targeted way.

Discussion

The higher education sector is undergoing a paradigm shift right now, with an increased emphasis on encouraging students to think creatively and entrepreneurially. There is a growing expectation that universities should equip their students with more than just academic knowledge; they should also equip them with the entrepreneurial skills necessary to thrive in today's uncertain and competitive global economy, where technological advancements occur at a dizzying pace. Introducing courses on creative entrepreneurship to universities in China has been a priority for the country's Ministry of Education. This has sparked a lot of interest in universities and colleges as a vital part of preparing students for the modern workforce and encouraging creativity.

There is a new field of research looking at how innovative entrepreneurship programs at universities affect the entrepreneurial actions of students and alumni as a result of the merging of these two areas of study. In light of the specifics of vocational higher education, this article investigates how introducing students to novel forms of entrepreneurship instruction influences their subsequent entrepreneurial actions. It delves deeply into this ever-changing area by classifying previous studies on innovative entrepreneurship teaching in tertiary vocational institutions and the entrepreneurial actions of college and university students. Future research trends, gaps, and opportunities are identified after a thorough examination of important empirical studies, theoretical frameworks, and conceptual contributions. Methodologies are also critically evaluated. By implementing novel approaches to entrepreneurship teaching at postsecondary vocational schools, we hope to better comprehend the myriad elements that shape entrepreneurial conduct.

When people talk about higher vocational education, they're really referring to a combination of the two. There is a direct correlation between the rising demand for highly qualified technical workers across the country and the expansion of vocational and technical education programs at the university level. There have been four main stages in the development of China's higher vocational education system. The first stage of integrating adult higher education, higher vocational education, and higher specialised education took place between 1998 and 2000. A variety of names, including "higher vocational" and "higher specialized education," were used to describe this type of education throughout this time (Sen, 2013). In addition, management techniques to control professional environments and talent supply were implemented during the era of standardized management (2001–2005), which also saw the introduction of a single professional catalogue. To further control school administration, the first round of operational evaluations was also instituted. This led to the eventual standardization of management procedures in universities offering vocational degrees (Xiaoqing, 2022). Also, "higher vocational education" slowly replaced "higher vocational and post-secondary education" over the connotation construction era of 2006–2013. Xiaoqing (2022) notes that as a result, universities and colleges with a focus on vocational education have moved their emphasis to connotation creation with an emphasis on professional development. Opportunities and resources for higher education have grown as a result of a shift in emphasis toward the creation of specialized programs and an improvement in overall academic standards at both four-year institutions and universities (Yu, 2022). The focus in the development of higher vocational education moved from reforms and constructions linked to teaching in the 2014 comprehensive reform stage to issues that impact career development beyond teaching. Consequently, important changes have been given more priority over time (Yu, 2022). Undergraduates are working to enhance vocational education by building specialized higher vocational institutions that mirror Chinese culture. A fundamental tenet of vocational education reform is the merging of academic and occupational curricula. At this point in time, comprehensive reform is also being advocated for as a novel component of vocational education's evolution.

Developing highly competent technical experts is one of the primary goals of vocational education, which includes higher vocational education (Yu, 2022). The goal of higher vocational education should be to strengthen undergraduate programs while they maintain their own identities beginning in 2021. We should work towards developing a system that integrates vocational education at the intermediate level, senior specialization, senior undergraduate, and professional postgraduate levels, as well as requirements for talent cultivation in undergraduate vocational programs. Revamping the system and creating a brand new vocational education track from the ground up is essential if we want vocational education to be more effective by 2023. Incorporating regional characteristics, strengthening standardized development, and improving regulations and systems that support the nurturing mode, development system, operation mechanism, and social security of vocational education are all important goals of this redesign. It should accurately reflect the characteristics of technical-skill-oriented education. Furthermore, it is critical to centralize the primary duty of municipalities and to set up transparent, systematic regulations on programs for cultivating talent, pedagogical approaches, practical systems for instruction, and faculty. Implementing these steps will guarantee the growth of top-notch vocational education that can adapt to the constantly changing demands of scientific, technological, and industrial progress (Mengqing & Jing, 2023). Market innovation, unmet technical needs, unsolved issues, and the "last kilometre" are the main points of discussion. The objective is to make vocational education a key factor in city development by enhancing the connection between industry and education. According to the Department (2023), this will generate fresh energy for social and economic development by promoting the education, talent, value, innovation, and industrial chains in tandem with one another. Explore new ways of working together internationally and make

higher vocational education more accessible worldwide. Xiaoqing (2022) argues that higher vocational education should gradually become more transparent in order to better connect and facilitate social and economic progress, improve development alignment, and ultimately contribute to building a proficient society and a prosperous nation with a skilled workforce.

The bulk of China's universities and vocational colleges were founded by provincial or municipal governments or business magnates; these institutions stand out because of the significant role they play in boosting regional economies (Lu & Chen, 2022). It is essential to change the way talent development is done at universities and vocational schools if we want our students to learn innovative entrepreneurship, be more adaptable, creative, and dedicated. Higher vocational college and university graduates will be prepared to meet societal expectations (X. G. Li, 2020). To help its graduates find work in today's competitive employment market, Chinese universities and vocational institutions have been using creative entrepreneurial education since the 1990s. These recent grads are under a lot of pressure to find jobs, but this pragmatic strategy will help. According to Liming and Fengjun (2020), creative entrepreneurship education is currently a hot topic at almost all of China's higher vocational colleges and universities. Providing creative entrepreneurial education is a primary focus for most universities and higher vocational institutes. Unfortunately, the intended result in this area has not been reached due to a number of issues. A lack of a strong system to develop creative minds, graduates with stale knowledge and no fresh ideas, and schools that don't encourage creativity and risk-taking among their pupils are all contributing issues (Ding, 2021).

Innovative entrepreneurship education at universities and vocational schools has matured over the past three decades, and in that time it has produced substantial findings from both theoretical and practical investigations. Higher vocational creative entrepreneurial programs are requesting more from their students in this new era. Xinghai (2021) predicts that ten development patterns will be seen in higher vocational innovative entrepreneurial education. Raising the profile of education is becoming more important, especially in advocating for the qualitative improvement of vocational education at the university level. The "Programme for the Construction of High-level Higher Vocational Schools and Programmes with Chinese Characteristics" lays out a plan for the future of vocational education, and education in creative entrepreneurship at the higher vocational level will play a major role in that plan. The development of creative, technically proficient individuals is an area where this education will be vital. The cultivation of creative, technically proficient individuals will rely heavily on new entrepreneurial programs (Liming & Fengjun, 2020). Education that encourages students to think creatively and entrepreneurially should take center stage in vocational colleges. Everyone should have access to high-quality, continuous education that they may use throughout their lives. Every student should have access to innovative entrepreneurship education that is part of a comprehensive talent development program. Not only should it help kids, but everyone in society should reap the benefits. Hence, innovative entrepreneurship education ought to be available to all students and the broader public (J. L. Wang, 2022). It is critical to incorporate creative entrepreneurship education into the full talent training process and deliver it to all students if we want to encourage employment and entrepreneurship. Everyone in society, not just schoolchildren, should have access to this kind of education. Workers in social enterprises should also have access to vocational education. In addition, meeting the demands of professionals for continuous education is crucial. The needs of the modern period are well-suited to the idea of teaching innovative entrepreneurship in vocational higher education programs. "Everyone can innovate and succeed" will be a philosophy that educators and students alike embrace, and the notion of "mass entrepreneurship and innovation" will gain societal acceptance. In conclusion, both instructors and students will hold the view that "education of the whole area and education of

the whole process" is essential. Education and whole process education" will become the core concept of innovative entrepreneurship education. The institutional mechanism will be more perfect, and higher vocational colleges will take the main responsibility to enhance the strategic position of innovative entrepreneurship education in the development of the school, implement the "hand project", and form the organisational and management system of innovative entrepreneurship education with diversified participation, unified leadership, concerted management, openness and cooperation, synergy and high efficiency, and the experts from inside and outside of the school will participate in the high-level decision-making, management and guidance of education and teaching reform, and form a system of "whole area education and whole process education". Management and guidance of education and teaching reforms, and formation of an operation mechanism of innovative entrepreneurship education in which all organisations cooperate with each other, make joint efforts to promote, and have a sound system and internal and external synergy(Xinghai, 2021). The national policy support system will be more powerful, and the education system of innovative entrepreneurship such as curriculum, project, culture, evaluation and platform will be perfected day by day. The education mode will be more innovative, and the "three-in-one" collaborative education mode combining school, enterprise and government will become the leading mode of innovative entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges and universities(weng, 2022). The reform of teachers, teaching materials and teaching method of innovative entrepreneurship education will become an important hand to promote the high-quality development of innovative entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges and universities. The curriculum system of innovative entrepreneurship education will be constantly improved and more complete(Xia, 2020). The platform service of innovative entrepreneurship education will be more open. Evaluation of innovative entrepreneurship education is an important link to promote the self-improvement of higher vocational innovative entrepreneurship education and to achieve the improvement of innovative entrepreneurship education performance, and to build the assessment and evaluation system at the macro, meso and micro levels, so as to make the evaluation of innovative entrepreneurship education more effective.

Deepening the reform of innovative entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges and universities is an urgent need for the implementation of the innovation-driven development strategy of the country and the promotion of economic quality, efficiency and upgrading, and it is also an important measure to promote the comprehensive reform of higher vocational education and higher-quality entrepreneurship and employment of graduates(R. Yang, 2023). Under the background of "mass entrepreneurship and innovation", the innovative entrepreneurship activities of college students are beneficial to the cultivation of new industries, the development of regional economy and economic transformation and upgrading(N. A. Thompson, Verduijn, & Gartner, 2020). However, the overall entrepreneurship rate of Chinese college students is low, and the survival rate of entrepreneurship is not high, and there are still many factors restricting the development potential of this group of entrepreneurs(X. G. Li, 2020). Innovative entrepreneurship education has become an important tool to promote the comprehensive reform of higher vocational education, which is of great practical significance to enhance the entrepreneurial behaviour of college students and promote economic progress and social employment(C. Zhao, 2020). The research on entrepreneurship education in higher vocational colleges is in a relatively backward situation, and not many studies have been conducted in this area(Deng, 2019). As entrepreneurship education has gradually become the teaching hotspot of innovative entrepreneurship education for students in higher vocational colleges and universities, research on the mechanism of entrepreneurship education influencing entrepreneurial behaviours of students in higher vocational colleges and universities can help to provide theoretical basis and empirical evidence for students in higher vocational colleges

and universities to carry out entrepreneurship education, so as to guide the innovative entrepreneurship practice of students in higher vocational colleges and universities in a more targeted way.

Conclusion

The literature on innovative entrepreneurship education primarily focuses on the concept, domestic research, and policy orientation, evaluation system, and innovative entrepreneurship ability. Foreign research on creative entrepreneurial education mostly concentrates on system development, faculty construction, and discipline creation, using the United States, Britain, and Germany as case studies. This analysis reveals the deficiencies in both domestic and foreign research on creative entrepreneurial education. Domestic research tends to prioritize theoretical guidance but lacks practical implementation, while foreign research emphasizes practical orientation but lacks robust scientific theoretical foundations.

The study on entrepreneurial intention can be categorized into three main components: the conceptual framework, the theoretical model, and the elements that influence it. The research on entrepreneurial intention conducted by domestic and international researchers is well-developed, comprehensive, and substantial. It is supported by a solid theoretical foundation and practical experience. This study incorporates relevant theoretical models. Nevertheless, the research on entrepreneurial intention lacks a comprehensive and organized integration, and its level of innovativeness requires enhancement throughout the course of time. The analysis of entrepreneurial intention reveals that the current impact on the entrepreneurial intention of college students primarily revolves around the personal traits of the entrepreneur, such as their motivation, attitude, and alertness towards entrepreneurship. There is a scarcity of literature that investigates the external factors influencing the entrepreneurial intention of college students. This paper focuses on researching college innovative entrepreneurship and categorizes it into two dimensions: school and individual. This approach broadens the investigation of the factors that influence college students' entrepreneurial intention to some extent.

The research on entrepreneurial self-efficacy has been extensively explored by scholars both domestically and internationally. This study builds upon the existing literature by integrating and extracting common dimensions of entrepreneurial self-efficacy, namely opportunity identification, innovative ability, and relationship coordination. Nevertheless, scholars have yet to establish a cohesive criterion for categorizing entrepreneurial self-efficacy into distinct dimensions. It is imperative to establish a measurement standard for further subdivision. This study focuses on measuring the self-efficacy of school students in order to delineate the dimensions of entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

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